

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

Ship and AUV observations near /within a warm ice-shelf cavity

Deliverable D2.3

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Cover sheet: AUV 'Ran' in front of Thwaites ice shelf, photo by Anna Wåhlin.

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1. Publishable summary

This deliverable consists of several data sets obtained during the Korean Polar research vessel Araon cruise to the Amundsen Sea, Antarctica. This report consists of a summary of the data gathered - the data sets themselves will be published in an open data repository once the quality control is completed.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

A successful cruise to the Amundsen Sea was conducted on the Korean icebreaker RVIB Araon between 28 December 2024 and 15 February 2024. In addition to the autonomous underwater vehicle (AUV) and ship data sets reported here, numerous data sets from drilling operations on land, helicopter-based sampling, and moored instrumentation was also obtained.

Fig. 1: Map of the cruise region. Symbols indicate all the stations that were conducted during the cruise. From Lee et al (2024).

2.1.1 AUV missions

A total of six dives were performed during the expedition. The last dive proved fatal, the AUV went missing. Figure 2 shows the location and mission tracks of each dive during the cruise. Ran has a suite of basic sensors (e.g., dual SBE19+ CTD systems, an EcoPuck, a HydroC carbon dioxide sensor, a DeepSUNA nitrate sensor,

Edgetech systems for side scan and sub bottom prifliers), and a number of sensors that are exchanged and/or not operated during each dive. Table 1 shows which sensors that were operated in each of the dives, and Figure 2 shows maps of the three dives.

Table 1: Summary of all the AUV dives undertaken during the cruise.

Dive	Launch date	Launch time	Dive length	Comments	Sensor suite
ANA14B_01	2024-01-07	05:58:18	22 h	Test dive in Ferrero Bay	Basic + Pinnacle ADCP + DL EM2040
ANA14B_02	2024-01-12	14:37:02	24 h	First dive underneath Thwaites	Basic + Pinnacle ADCP + DL EM2040
ANA14B_03	2024-01-15	23:28:44	25 h	Second dive underneath Thwaites	Basic + Pinnacle ADCP + DL EM2040
ANA14B_04b	2024-01-22	01:50:33	21 h	Dive following the ice base at Thwaites	Basic + UL EM2040CX + Water sampler
ANA14B_05	2024-01-26	05:04:00	26 h	Dive following the ice base at Dotson	Basic + UL EM2040CX + Water sampler
ANA14_B_06	2024-01-28	05:00:00	26 h	AUV never returned from mission	Basic + UL EM2040CX + Water sampler

In total, 874 km was covered during the six dives, of which 637 km were under ice. After the end of the last mission the AUV never returned to its programmed meeting point and is assumed lost below Dotson ice shelf (the target for this last mission was to repeat a previous mission that was conducted successfully in 2022).

Figure 2: Map showing the location of the five successful AUV missions.

2.1.2 CTD data from the AUV

Ran is equipped with dual systems for conductivity and temperature (SBE19+) and oxygen (SBE43), pumped

with two SBE5T pumps, one for each system. Figure 3 shows a photo of the two systems mounted inside the AUV.

Fig. 3: The two CTD systems mounted inside the AUV. Photo: Anna Wåhlin

Problems with the starboard CTD system

The conductivity in the starboard CTD appears to have been drifting in between missions (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Drift of the starboard CTD system. Panels show Absolute salinity (SA) versus conservative temperature (CT) for the three missions below Thwaites ice shelf. Red markers show data from ANA14B_02 (a, d), ANA14B_03 (b, e) and ANA14B_04b (c, f), based on the starboard CTD package (top panels) and the port CTD package (bottom panels). Black semitransparent markers show data from missions 2, 3 and 4 in all panels. The difference between missions of the deep water in top panels is due to the starboard sensor drift.

On the first of the missions, the starboard CTD system was not operating. In the following four missions it was operational, and when the drift was discovered it was decided to use the port CTD for all missions (mission 1 - 5).

Offset from ship CTD

The conductivity offset between the starboard AUV package and the ship CTD was 0.001 S/m. This will be updated after post cruise calibration of ship CTD.

Dissolved oxygen

In the first mission, the starboard oxygen sensor was broken, and the port one did not record any data. In the second mission the starboard sensor was replaced to SBE43-2637, but the offset was found to be very high (recorded -1.02 ml/l in deep water below Thwaites, compared to the ship CTD). The port sensor was found to be broken.

In the third mission the port SBE43 was replaced to SBE43-3700, and the offset on this sensor was found to be zero compared to the ship CTD. This sensor was used for missions 3, 4 and 5.

Table 2: Summary of the CTD sensors used and offset for each mission.

Mission	CTD system	SBE43	offset C (S/m)	offset T (°C)	offset DO (ml/l)
ANA14B_01	Port	-	0.001	0	-
ANA14B_02	Port	SBE43-2637	0.001	0	-1.02
ANA14B_03	Port	SBE43-3700	0.001	0	0
ANA14B_04b	Port	SBE43-3700	0.001	0	0
ANA14B_05	Port	SBE43-3700	0.001	0	0
ANA14B_06	Port	SBE43-3700	0.001	0	0

2.1.3 Water sampler data

The water sampler was mounted when we did not have the Pinnacle ADCP mounted (i.e. missions ANA14B_04, ANA14B_05 and ANA14B_06). Due to some changes in the software, all the samples in ANA14B_04 failed. Thus, only one mission (ANA14B_05) had correct water samples. The location for the samples are shown in Figure 5, and the average properties of each water sample is shown in Table 3.

Fig. 5: Maps showing the AUV tracks and location of water samples in mission ANA14B_05. Gray area indicates the ice shelf, black markers show the locations during which the water sampler was pumping water into each sample, and the color indicates (a) Dissolved oxygen (b) meltwater fraction (c) Conservative temperature according to color bars.

Table 3: Position, depth, conservative temperature, absolute salinity, and dissolved oxygen for the 14 water samples taken during mission ANA14B_05. The first sample is a blank.

Sample	Lat	Lon	Depth (m)	C_T (deg)	S_A (g/kg)	DO (ml/l)
1	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN	NaN
2	-74.2143201857258	-112.026192773713	695.947278030303	0.37806862618712	34.6592316703508	4.43711035720792
3	-74.2225696708301	-112.023284965046	724.187048232323	0.418616974192186	34.6752885868674	4.42871679012104
4	-74.2356217491967	-112.032859161685	732.981240656566	0.4045388629207	34.6719191023267	4.42511743525427
5	-74.3028688384737	-112.109711620054	429.990906060606	-0.449077213775486	34.4256835245945	4.8576946077954
6	-74.3026751846947	-112.119093376109	429.99319520202	-0.41600850464027	34.4277799628541	4.81596677892104
7	-74.3027736809985	-112.129270974338	429.988541414141	-0.40325018928404	34.4295384190636	4.81428618535865
8	-74.3715581014116	-112.515025054837	459.985309343434	-0.403859964344684	34.4125334236934	4.67573376431762
9	-74.3626104313679	-112.521137623587	460.00602550505	-0.468264309983292	34.3974630376764	4.72962620040007
10	-74.3718263769545	-112.525503976448	459.987881818182	-0.393058844525884	34.4139293383339	4.6691258029446
11	-74.3625245689853	-112.531639874659	460.002183333333	-0.410509626995828	34.4072543699262	4.67528254192713
12	-74.372035371053	-112.535989897826	459.985880808081	-0.380833484991235	34.4159492924681	4.66253117349533
13	-74.3624834042525	-112.542148594918	460.005157323232	-0.402795597646183	34.4076567088646	4.66860154294253
14	-74.3722341763957	-112.546481945631	459.992295454546	-0.373102649700447	34.4172260493537	4.66194641896243

2.1.4. Acoustic and optical sensors on the AUV

Downward-looking multibeam

Ran is equipped with a EM2040 downward-looking multibeam. The system was operated on ANA14B_01, ANA14B_02, and ANA14B_03. Preliminary versions of the data sets were left on the cruise NAS drive. Post processing steps remaining is to QC the data more carefully and to apply the post processed navigation data with the processing.

Upward-looking multibeam

Ran is equipped with a EM2040CX upward-looking multibeam. The system was operated on ANA14B_04b, ANA14B_05, and ANA14B_06. Preliminary versions of the data sets were left on the cruise NAS drive. Post

processing steps remaining is to QC the data more carefully and to apply the post processed navigation data with the processing.

EcoPuck data

Ran is equipped with an FLBBDC6k EcoPuck with serial number 5028. The system was operated on all missions and is part of the basic suite of sensors. Preliminary versions of the data sets were left on the cruise NAS drive. Post processing steps remaining is to apply the post processed navigation data with the processing.

2.1.5 Long range ADCP data

An upward-looking Pinnacle long range ADCP (45 kHz) was mounted on the AUV for three missions: one in Fererro bay (ANA14B_01) and two under the eastern part of Thwaites ice shelf (ANA14B_02, ANA14B_03). The ADCP was run in narrow band mode, with a range of 1300 m, cell size of 32 m and pinging every 2.4 s (ANA14B_01) and 4 s (ANA14B_02, ANA14B_03) respectively.

During the first mission under Thwaites (ANA14B_02), the ADCP stopped recording data after 14.5 hours. The problem was likely related to the internal memory card. We reformatted the memory card before the third mission and had no problems during the third mission.

Fig. 6: Back scatter data for the three missions that had the Pinnacle mounted and operating a (time in UTC).

The raw velocity data from the ADCP looks good for the entire water column, and we should be able to extract

currents from it. The raw data needs to be processed and remapped to remove the AUVs own movement and to compensate for the AUVs pitching and rolling movement, which has not been done yet.

Back scatter amplitude data from the ADCP was used to create a low-resolution map of the ice draft (Fig. 6), aiding the planning of the third mission under Thwaites (ANA14B_04b), where the AUV went closer to the ice. Code for deriving ice draft from the back scatter data is uploaded here:

https://github.com/stinawahlgren/hugin_pinnacle_surface_track

2.2 References

Lee, W. S. et al, 2024. Thwaites Glacier Expedition 2023–2024 (ANA14B). Cruise report. KOPRI is planning to make it available in open access and OCEAN:ICE will share it on its website as soon as available.

2.3 Open Science

All data sets will be published in the open repository Swedish National Data Service: <https://www.snd.se/sv>
All results will be published in open access scientific journals with vigorous peer review. A publication is planned in 2025.

3. Results

The main results of this deliverable is in the form of several data sets, presented herein.

4. Impact

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following objectives of the project as described in the description of the action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica, particularly relating to ice sheet-ocean interaction and deep water formation and export.

This deliverable provides new data reducing the spatial gaps in ocean observations inside ice shelf cavities. In particular it brings in five new data sets from two different 'warm' cavity systems. The new data will aid to assessments of the oceanic controls on heat and freshwater delivery to and from 'cold' (e.g. Weddell Sea) as well as 'warm' (Amundsen Sea) sites of ice sheet-ocean interaction around Antarctica, and the processes that control mixing, water mass formation and export over the continental shelves and subpolar basins.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models, using historical observations and new data sets obtained in the project.

This deliverable provides new unique data of the ice base that gives clues to the ice-ocean processes creating melt in ice shelf cavities. Particularly under warm and cold ice shelves and around grounded icebergs, including vertical/horizontal mixing, ocean heat delivery, iceberg interactions with sea-ice and bathymetry and basal melt. Implement these improvements in coupled ice sheet-ocean and ice sheet-climate models.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet and coupled ice sheet-climate models.

This deliverable contributes by providing new data that can be used to calibrate and 'sanity check' models of ice sheets and ice sheet-climate models. By using new and existing datasets to improve ice sheet model initialisation and quantifying the uncertainty in present day freshwater fluxes from Antarctica due to climate variability, dynamical processes (calving, ice flow) and surface/basal mass balance (surface runoff, basal melt).

O7: Deliver free and open access to all data obtained in the project and contribute to international assessments (e.g. IPCC), climate model development, multi-national ocean observing initiatives (e.g. SOOS, All-Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance) and policymakers.

This deliverable contributes by providing five new data sets from unique Antarctic settings, including underneath ice shelves. The published data sets will be openly accessible and findable. Data consolidation and delivery will be achieved through close integration with SOOS, EMODnet and Copernicus data delivery services and will follow FAIR principles and be INSPIRE compliant. Direct partnership with SOOS, SAMOC, EPB, EU Polar Cluster, EU-PolarNet 2, and other European and international programmes, as well as the high-level involvement of investigators in international science coordination, climate assessment and policy bodies will maximise the reach and impact of OCEAN:ICE.